

under transplanted culture. Straw yield of Sasyashree was higher than that of Vikash in direct seeded culture, but they performed equally well when they were transplanted.

Neither culture type nor variety significantly influenced total N uptake in rice, although their interaction effect was significant. N uptake in Vikash was significantly more under transplanted condition than that of IET7959, but in direct seeded culture, the opposite was true. Vikash and IET9978 can be used for direct seeding. The two varieties also removed significantly less N when direct seeded than when they were transplanted (see table). ■

Yields and N uptake of six rice varieties under two cultures in a submerged Ustorthent. Ramachandrapuram, AP, India, 1990 WS.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)			Straw yield (t/ha)			Total N uptake (kg/ha)		
	DS ^a	TP ^b	Mean	DS	TP	Mean	DS	TP	Mean
Rasi	4.6	4.1	4.4	4.2	3.3	3.7	89.8	85.6	87.7
Sasyashree	4.0	3.5	3.7	4.8	4.5	4.7	86.2	82.4	84.3
Vikash	4.4	4.4	4.4	3.9	4.4	4.1	78.4	89.9	84.1
IET7959	4.6	4.2	4.4	3.7	3.4	3.6	88.8	81.5	85.1
IET9219	4.9	4.3	4.6	4.2	3.4	3.8	85.6	81.7	83.7
IET9978	4.4	4.4	4.4	3.8	3.8	3.8	79.4	92.3	85.8
Mean	4.5	4.2		4.1	3.8		84.7	85.6	
LSD (0.05)									
Culture (C)		ns ^c			ns			ns	
Variety (V)		0.34			0.44			ns	
C × V		ns							
C at same V					0.72			10.0	
V at same C					0.62			8.0	

^aDS = direct seeded. ^bTP = transplanted. ^cns = not significant.

Integrated pest management—diseases

Occurrence of rice grain rot disease in Vietnam

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Rice grain rot disease has caused damage in Japan, Taiwan, Philippines, and Latin America. The disease causal organism is bacterium *Pseudomonas glumae*.

Symptoms are discolored grain, husk, and endosperm. Grain is unfilled in severely infected plants.

The disease was first recorded in Vietnam in 1991 early summer rice season in the central provinces and in the summer rice season in the Red River Delta provinces. PPRI studied the disease etiology and its distribution. About 100,000 ha were infected in 1992 early summer and summer seasons. Five provinces (Ha Tay, Thai Binh, Nam Ha, Thanh Hoa, and Khanh Hoa) are reported to be disease hot spots, with crop losses of up to 75%.

To confirm the causal agent of the disease, infected grains were collected. Two botanic parasitic bacteria were isolated and identified in the laboratory. One had a yellow colony and the other, a creamy white colony. Seedborne fungi *Cercospora*, *Helminthosporium*, and *Curvularia* were also isolated.

Variety CR203, which is widely grown in the Red River Delta was artificially inoculated at the heading stage. Only the bacterium with the creamy white colony at 10⁸ cfu/ml concentration produced symptoms similar to the disease observed in the field; it was designated as isolate no. 18.

We used the method of Matsuda et al to detect *P. glumae* using a CaC₂O₄ crystal. We cultured isolate no. 18 in a potato-peptone-glucose-agar (PPGA) mixed medium and with 0.1% CaCl₂ at 38 °C. The color of the PPGA turned a pale greenish yellow, and the CaC₂O₄ crystal on the colony was observed under the microscope. *P. glumae* was identified as the causal organism. ■

Treating rice seeds with fungicides and antagonists to control seedborne diseases

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Rice blast (Bl), caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav., and brown leaf spot, caused by *Helminthosporium oryzae* Breda de Haan, are seedborne diseases that cause appreciable yield loss. We treated rice seeds with some fungicides and antagonists to assess effects on seed viability, seedling vigor, and inhibition of seedborne pathogens.

We conducted standard blotter assays using seeds of rice cultivar ADT36. *P. oryzae* infected 27.0% of the seeds and *H. oryzae*, 35.4%. Seeds were treated with fungicides and antagonists (see table), shade-dried, and stored for 5 mo. Seed viability and seedling vigor were

assessed monthly for 6 mo by roll towel method. Inhibition zone assay was used to determine inhibition of pathogens.

In the roll towel method, 10-d-old normal seedlings were selected randomly and root length, shoot length, and dry weights were measured.

Vigor index (VI) was calculated as

$$\begin{aligned} \text{VI} &= \text{Germination \%} \times \text{root length} \\ &\quad (\text{mean of 10 seedlings, in cm}) \\ &= \text{Germination \%} \times \text{shoot length} \\ &\quad (\text{mean of 10 seedlings, in cm}) \\ &= \text{Germination \%} \times \text{dry weight} \\ &\quad (\text{mean of 10 seedlings, in mg}). \end{aligned}$$

In the inhibition zone assay, the spore suspension (10⁶ spores/ml) of the test pathogen (*P. oryzae* or *H. oryzae*) was mixed with molten potato dextrose agar medium and poured in petri plates. A treated seed was placed at the center of the medium. The diameter of the

Effect of treating seed with chemicals and antagonists on inhibiting seedborne pathogens and on germination, root length, shoot length, dry weight, and vigor indices.*

Treatment	Concentration (%)	Diameter of inhibition zone for <i>P. oryzae</i> (mm)	Diameter of inhibition zone for <i>H. oryzae</i> (mm)	Germination (%)	Root length (cm)	Shoot length (cm)	Dry weight (mg)	Vigor index based on root length and percent germination	Vigor index based on shoot length and percent germination	Vigor index based on dry matter and percent germination
Fungicide										
Pyroquilon	0.1	22.90 c	15.47 b	95.11 ab	16.12 fg	6.22 a	151.70 jk	1536.16 q	592.55 p	14441.78 q
Pyroquilon	0.2	30.11 ab	18.39 g	94.89 ab	16.50 efg	6.49 a	152.44 j	1565.90 p	616.67 o	14471.78 p
Pyroquilon	0.3	30.77 a	19.33 fg	93.78 b	16.37 fg	6.05 a	150.17 jkl	1536.22 q	568.25 q	14088.17 r
Tricyclazole	0.1	20.45 c-f	21.94 def	94.67 ab	16.99 d-g	6.61 a	158.22 i	1610.47 o	625.92 n	14989.56 o
Tricyclazole	0.2	27.44 b	25.06 cd	96.00 ab	18.81 a-f	7.18 a	164.61 gh	1808.12 j	689.65 i	15011.33 n
Tricyclazole	0.3	27.50 b	26.39 bc	95.56 ab	18.60 a-f	6.85 a	161.56 h	1782.84 l	655.10 l	15446.89 m
Carbendazim	0.1	15.22 ghi	22.22 def	95.34 ab	21.05 ab	7.77 a	175.56 ab	2054.78 b	755.73 b	17091.55 b
Carbendazim	0.2	21.56 cd	24.11 cde	97.11 ab	21.77 a	7.90 a	176.22 a	2119.58 a	769.75 a	17156.67 a
Carbendazim	0.3	22.11 cd	25.00 cd	97.33 a	20.53 abc	7.23 a	174.67 ab	1972.14 d	727.91 f	16771.33 e
Carboxin	0.1	14.83 hi	21.67 ef	96.00 ab	17.50 c-g	7.01 a	165.61 fg	1674.35 n	669.17 j	15830.67 k
Carboxin	0.2	18.22 efg	22.94 de	95.78 ab	20.31 abc	7.59 a	174.61 ab	1909.41 f	735.02 d	16884.22 c
Carboxin	0.3	19.06 def	24.00 cde	96.00 ab	19.77 a-e	7.59 a	172.94 bc	1892.87 h	694.81 h	16535.33 g
Mancozeb	0.2	14.11 i	29.50 b	94.67 ab	16.53 efg	6.82 a	165.61 fg	1562.86 p	646.74 m	15642.67 l
Mancozeb	0.3	19.67 def	33.28 a	95.56 ab	17.82 b-g	7.31 a	169.61 de	1703.46 m	699.04 g	16209.78 i
Mancozeb	0.4	19.72 def	33.00 a	95.34 ab	18.73 a-f	7.67 a	171.44 cd	1786.86 k	731.94 e	16347.11 h
Thiram	0.2	12.28 i	18.50 g	96.22 ab	19.76 a-e	6.84 a	173.72 abc	1901.47 g	658.44 k	16719.77 f
Thiram	0.3	15.06 hi	23.33 cde	97.11 ab	20.39 abc	7.67 a	175.03 ab	1980.98 c	745.37 c	17093.94 b
Thiram	0.4	17.50 fgh	24.84 cde	96.45 ab	20.03 a-d	7.61 a	174.61 ab	1941.22 e	735.00 de	16859.55 d
Antagonists										
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	60 × 10 ⁹ cfu/ml	15.06 hi	18.50 g	93.78 b	16.15 fg	5.99 a	149.33 kl	1515.89 r	562.49 r	13930.22 s
<i>Pseudomonas fluorescens</i>	60 × 10 ⁹ cfu/ml	14.83 hi	19.83 fg	93.78 b	16.11 fg	6.04 a	147.78 lm	1512.69 s	553.41 s	13857.28 t
Carbendazim (0.2%) + <i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	60 × 10 ⁹ cfu/ml	21.22 cde	23.17 cde	94.67 ab	19.67 a-e	6.54 a	167.94 ef	1858.51 i	619.47 o	15939.78 j
Control		0.00 j	0.00 i	88.45 c	15.15 g	5.73 a	144.94 m	1341.63 t	507.18 t	12889.00 u
LSD (P = 0.05)		0.66	0.68	3.40	0.07	0.02	0.90	46.30	11.80	282.69

*Av of 3 replications of 6 mo of observations. Values followed by different letters in each column are significantly different (P = 0.05) by DMRT.

inhibition zone that developed around the seed was measured.

Seeds treated with pyroquilon (0.3%) had the largest inhibition zone for *P. oryzae*, followed by tricyclazole (0.3%), mancozeb (0.4%), and carboxin (0.3%). Seeds treated with mancozeb (0.4%) had the largest inhibition zone for *H. oryzae*, followed by tricyclazole (0.3%). Carbendazim and carboxin (both at 0.2 and 0.3%) also inhibited the pathogens (see table).

Treated seeds showed higher seedling vigor than untreated seeds. Seedlings raised from seeds treated with carbendazim (0.2%) and mancozeb (0.4%) had the best seedling vigor.

It is advisable to treat seeds with either pyroquilon or tricyclazole (0.2%) in areas

where BI and brown leaf spot disease are severe. These fungicides effectively inhibit the pathogens while maintaining vigorous seedlings. Significantly higher seedling vigor, germination percentage,

and inhibition of seedborne pathogens can also be obtained by treating seeds with carbendazim (0.2%) and mancozeb (0.3%). ■

Effect of foliar spraying of *Aspergillus terreus* Thom on sheath blight (ShB) and rice plant characteristics

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We tested the efficacy of *A. terreus* as an aqueous spore suspension spray in reducing incidence of ShB (*Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn).

The experiment was conducted during 1988 and 1992 ahu seasons (Apr-Aug). Twenty-six-day-old seedlings of rice cultivar IR50 were transplanted into 25-cm-diam clay pots containing 5 kg ricefield soil. *A. terreus* conidial suspension (47 × 10⁶ spores/ml in 1988 and 49 × 10⁶ spores/ml in 1992) was sprayed on foliage 38 d after transplanting in three ways: 3 d after, 3 d before, and simultaneously with inoculation of *R. Solani*. *R. solani*